

Implementation of Knowledge Management in Building the Organization Dealing Effectiveness of Dynamic Environment in the Disruptive Era

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ABSTRACT: The focus of this study is the implementation of knowledge management, organizational effectiveness, and disruptive which uses a descriptive narrative approach to describe knowledge management as a multi-disciplinary approach. The method used is the descriptive qualitative analytic approach. Data collected through literature studies and fieldwork using interviews, observation and documentation study.

The results showed that knowledge management is the organization's activities in managing knowledge as assets in which the various strategies are the proper distribution of knowledge to the right people and in the period of rapid so that they are can be interacting, share knowledge and apply it in their daily work to improve organizational performance. The results of this study are expected in the era of globalization where changes in environmental changes occur very rapidly, the uncertainty of the environment and the level of competition is very high often cause a leader should be able to have a strategy in making organizational decisions, errors in reading the situation and overreact to changes in the dynamically changing environment will fail. The organization will survive forward if managers can make the right decisions and quickly following the development of the internal and external environment.

KEYWORDS: Knowledge Management, Organizational Effectiveness, Dynamic Environment, Disruptive Era

I. INTRODUCTION

Dynamics of changes in technology and the external environment provide volatility to the organization (Felin & Powell, 2016). This is indicated by the increasingly short product cycles, changing tastes of people who are getting faster, and competition intensiveness until resources are increasingly scarce. The state requires human resources that exist in the organization must find new sources of competitive, which is rare, difficult to imitate, and can be used continuously in a sustainable manner. In the 21st century, globalization is worldwide. Advances in technology, transformation, telecommunications, and information have influenced individuals to cope with all the challenges in the face of a life full of competition. The amendment was to encourage individuals to move quickly to keep up with technology and knowledge. This is where the importance of organizational change and transformation to adapt to these changes through knowledge management and change management are effective and efficient.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Knowledge Management

Gellweiler, (2018) expressed in the theory of resource-based view of the firm (RBV), that resource is said to be positioned if it fulfills the criteria of a rare, valuable, difficult to imitate and hard to replace. The theory of a knowledge-based view of the firm (KBV) supports the view that knowledge is the most strategic resources for fulfilling the above criteria (Caner, Cohen & Pil, 2017); (Novianti, 2019).

The definition is in line with the statement Shattock (2018) concerning the organization of learning in which the parties conduct learning activities is the human resources of an organization (Shattock, 2018). Rowley & Farrow, (2018), gives the sense that knowledge is organized so that the information can be applied to solving the problem. The definition was supported by Holotiuk & Moormann (2018), which says that knowledge is information that has been analyzed and organized so that they can

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understand and use to solve problems and make decisions. To obtain optimal benefit from the knowledge possessed by human resources in an organization, it takes the management of knowledge called knowledge management.

Beyadar & Gardali (2011) define knowledge management as, any process or practice of creating, acquiring, capturing, sharing and using knowledge, wherever they may be, are beneficial for improving learning and performance in organizations. Knowledge management in an organization is done by Beyadar & Gardali (2011) identifying the knowledge possessed by all human resources and use it as a competitive advantage. At least eight processes of knowledge management: (1) the process of goal setting knowledge, (2) the process of identification of knowledge, (3) the acquisition of knowledge, (4) the process of development of knowledge, (5) the sharing and distribution of knowledge, (6) the utilization of knowledge, (7) the maintenance and storage of knowledge (knowledge retention), and (8) the process of evaluation and measurement of knowledge (knowledge assessment). However simplified by Obeidat et al, (2016) to three of the most popular process - because most often applied - is the process of knowledge acquisition, knowledge sharing, and knowledge utilization process. Mohajan et al (2017) is one of the pioneers in the field of knowledge management and was the first to publish a series of literature that bring concepts relevant management that is directly focused on the topic. Its overall framework is based on the foundation and the three pillars (Mohajan et al, 2017). The foundation and the three pillars of knowledge management are shown in Figure 1.

Source: (Wiig, 1997)

Figure 1. Three Pillars of Knowledge Management

Mohajan et al (2017), also assist in determining the different levels of the internationalization process of knowledge management. Internationalization level ranges are grouped into different modes such as lay (novice), beginner, competent, expert, and masters. Lay groups almost no awareness about knowledge and how to use it. The expert group could know and understand to apply knowledge of the workplace without any intervention.

The model knowledge management framework built by Wiig (1997) is then developed by Pencheva, (2018) called the "conversion of knowledge". The model identifies four types of knowledge conversion that drives the creation of knowledge: socialization, externalization, internalization, and combinations. This conversion is based on the dichotomy between tacit and explicit knowledge.

Tacit knowledge refers to knowledge that cannot be easily expressed verbally and articulated, while explicit knowledge refers to knowledge that can be easily expressed verbally in formal and systematic language. Later models of this framework are developed (Pencheva, 2018) into four modes of knowledge conversion. Four conversion modes are identified tacit knowledge to tacit (socialization); tacit to explicit (externalization); explicit to explicit (combination), and explicit to tacit (internalization). After undergoing a process of internalization, then knowledge will be included in the metaphor of the "spiral" of knowledge creation is often referred to as the SECI models.

Socialization is the process of creating knowledge by converting tacit knowledge from one entity (individual, group, or organization) to another entity. The combination is the process of creating new explicit knowledge of existing explicit knowledge. Conversion of tacit knowledge into explicit knowledge is called externalization. Conversion of explicit knowledge

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into tacit knowledge is called internalization. Organizational knowledge is created by the interaction between the four of this conversion process and through the transfer of tacit knowledge / explicit from individual to group all organizational levels.

Figure 2. SECI model (Farnese et al, 2019)

Further knowledge management framework was developed (Holsapple & Joshi, 1999). The model consists of seven knowledge management process that can operate at organizational knowledge. As depicted in Figure 3. This process of creating, identifying, collecting, customizing, managing, implementing, and sharing. This model identifies four determinants of an organization that facilitates the knowledge management process namely: leadership, measurement, culture, technology.

Source: (Holsapple & Joshi, 1999)

Figure 3. Organizational Knowledge Management Model

The model framework of knowledge management is the Liao et al (2017), in sense-making knowledge management model Liao et al (2017) which focuses on making sense, knowledge creation, decision making skills. Liao et al (2017) explained that these three processes are very interconnected and play an important role in expanding the vision of organizational knowledge, the potential for knowledge creation and its commitment to generate full knowledge illustration the Choo sense-making knowledge management model is shown in Figure 4

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Figure 4. The Choo Sense-Making Knowledge Management Model

Making Sense - long-term goal is the assurance that the organization will adapt and continue to thrive in a dynamic and complex environment through the activities of search and interpretation of appropriate information to enable it to understand the changes, trends, and scenarios about clients, suppliers, competitors, and another external environmental offender. Knowledge Creation- a process that allows companies to create or acquire, organize and process the information to generate new knowledge through organizational learning. Decision Making Skills- companies should choose the best option among the things that make sense and are presented and pursued by the strategy of the organization. The company's decision-making process is limited by the principle of bounded rationality.

In addition to enterprise-based organizations, libraries also implementing knowledge management in its operations. Until the framework model formed the acquisition, development, access, and management (ADAM) of knowledge (Khasawneh et al, 2016); (Idrees, 2012). The model (ADAM) was first invented around 2001 by a library Lahore University of Management and Technology, and the Institute of Leadership and Management. The ADAM model is shown in Figure 5.

Source: (Idrees, 2012)
Figure 5. Model ADAM

The knowledge management transfer process takes place repeatedly and forms a cycle and leads to knowledge that continues to evolve. Element management system intended to allow the organization with knowledge management becomes always creative, innovative and efficient. To have high competitiveness for the long term. Organizations or companies that do not manage their knowledge properly so that the knowledge transfer does not occur. Organizations need to manage the knowledge of its members at all levels. The purpose is:

- Knowing the power/placement throughout human resources
- Reuse of existing knowledge
- Speed up to process of creating new knowledge from existing knowledge
- Keeping the organization remains stable movement although an outflow of incoming HR

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The concept of effectiveness and performance of the Organization

To understand the effectiveness and performance of the organization, need a deep understanding of the organization (Devi, 2017). Understanding the organization Soda and Furlotti (2017) states that the organization is a tool used by humans to coordinate actions to get his wish or anything of value in order achieving goals. Likewise, according to Birken et al (2017) states that the organization as follows: "organization are: (1) social entities that (2) are goals are directed (3) are designed as deliberately structured and coordinate system activity, and (4) are linked to the external environment".

According to Liebowitz (2019) that "organization is a pattern of rules and a blueprint for reviews their co-ordination". According to Officer (2018) states that "organization is a deliberate arrangement of people to accomplish some specific purpose". From the opinions of the above, it can be concluded that the organization is a lakeside gathering place of people as members of the organization who have interests and objectives in common with basic tasks, functions, roles, and responsibilities are clear and obey all rules and follow the rules and procedures that apply, receive, understand and implement the values / norms tradition together consistently for solving and achieving the goals of the organization (Argyris, 2017).

According to Olkiewicz (2018), the effectiveness of the organization can be implemented properly depending on the role of a manager are:

1. Control: Namely the ability to control the external environment, and attract resources for the benefit of the organization and attract customers
2. Innovation: Namely ability and organizational skills to find new products and processes, including creating a new organizational structure and culture that can enhance the company's ability to change, adapt and evolve.
3. Efficiency, the ability to develop new production facilities, new technologies that can distribute products in a timely and cost of the most efficient, including the use of Internet-based information systems, total quality management and just-in-time inventory system to improve productivity.

Performance measurement is part of a management control system that includes both actions that imply planning decisions as well as employee performance evaluation and operation. Assessment of performance used by management to manage the operations of the organization effectively and efficiently through motivating employees to the maximum, to help decision-making is concerned with employees such as promotion, transfer, and dismissal, identify the needs and development of employees, as well as to provide feedback for employees about how his boss assess their performance and provide a basis for the distribution of awards.

Performance is the result of a planned process-specific job at the time and places the individual, group or organization concerned. This means that the performance consists of three components: quality, quantity, and effectiveness. According to Bozionelos et al (2016), a term derived from the performance of job performance or the actual performance (actual job performance or achievements attained by someone). Performance as a function of the interaction of ability or abilities (A), motivation or motivation (M), and the chance or opportunity (O) is the performance of (f) = A x M x O. It can be interpreted performance is influenced by factors ability, motivation, and opportunity.

The performance as a result of a person's overall success rate during certain periods of duty compared to the wide range of possibilities, such as the standard of the work, the target has been determined in advance. Performance measures can be seen from the side of a certain quantity and quality, according to standards organizations or companies. The form can be tangible and intangible, depending seen from the results and outcomes (Bozionelos et al, 2016).

Bozionelos et al (2016) to suggest that the factors affecting the performance of which is the capability and motivation factors (motivation). According to Uloli et al (2017) are four main things that affect the performance of employees, namely: (1) The employee motivation; (2) The ability and skills of employees; (3) Clarity and reception duties; and (4) The opportunity to perform. BCS (Balance Score Card) and MBCfPE (Malcom Baldrige Criteria for Performance Excellent) is one of the proper techniques are used to measure the performance of the organization.

Grow this the early stages of the life cycle of a company where the company has a product or service that has the best growth potential. In the growth stage, the company is operating with negative cash flow at a low rate of return on capital. The measurement used at this stage is the level of earnings or sales growth in market segments that have been targeted. Sustain is the second stage in which the company is still investment and reinvestment by hinting best returns.

The financial perspective is still used because financial measures are essential in providing a summary of the economic consequences of actions already taken. Financial performance measures provide clues on whether the company's strategy, implementation, and execution contributed or not to the increase in corporate profits. In the customer perspective, managers identify the customer and market segments where the business unit to compete and a variety of performance measures for businesses in target segments.

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In the internal business process perspective, According to Berends et al (2016), the identification process is carried out in advance to get the right size in the internal business process perspective. In general, the process consists of innovation, operations, and after-sales services. The innovation process is done by identifying customer needs and create products or services required. The operation process is a process to create and deliver a product or service.

The process of learning and growth factors rooted in human resources, systems, and procedures of the organization. This perspective is included in employee training and corporate culture associated with the improvement of individuals and organizations. According to Berends et al (2016) the perspective of learning and growth comes from three principles, namely: (1) The ability of workers. The labor which is owned by the company has led the company to provide access to information more feasible for employees to improve the efficiency in achieving the objectives of the company. (2) The ability of Information Systems (IS), is determined by the availability of information, the level of accuracy of the information and the period necessary to obtain such information. (3) Motivation, empowerment, and alignment. To create the necessary motivation organizational climate capable of creating the information itself and encourage the initiative of employees.

A strategic management system has four advantages, namely: (1) Comprehensive. Includes a non-financial perspective as a customer perspective, internal business processes, learning, and growth. Steer the company into a means of strategic facilities in the three perspectives the main cause resulting financial performance. (2) Coherent. The existence of a causal link between the resulting output systems strategy formulation and output generated by the system of strategic planning. (3) Balanced. The balance of strategic targets generated by the system of strategic planning is important for generating long-term financial performance. (4) Measured, is a measurable customer perspective, internal business processes, learning, and growth.

Objective criteria for performance excellence by (Indonesian Quality Award Foundation, 2007), designed to help organizations take an integrated approach in managing performance that boils down to (1) Submission of the best values that can be made to customers and stakeholders, contributing to the security and sustainability organization; (2) The improvement of the effectiveness and capability of the company or organization as a whole; and (3) Occurrence of organizational learning and teaching employees. Reasons for using MBCfPE in measuring management performance is because it can increase the process speed and quality, building high working system, translate vision and mission into strategies, and build customer loyalty.

The approach used in the score for the category of results is related to the LTCI which stands Level (level of performance), Trend, Comparison, and integration (cohesion). Classification according to MBCfPE world performance class consists of eight levels of performance, eight levels of performance are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Classification Class MBCfPE Performance

Classification Class Company	Score	Global Performance Company
<i>Poor</i>	0-275	<i>Early Development</i>
	276-375	<i>Early Result</i>
<i>Global Average</i>	376-475	<i>Early Improvement</i>
	476-575	<i>Good Performance</i>
	576-675	<i>Emerging Industry Leader</i>
<i>Global Image Excellent</i>	676-775	<i>Industry Leader</i>
	776-875	<i>benchmark Leader</i>
	876 - 1000	<i>World-Class Leader</i>

Environmental dynamics destructive era in the era of globalization where changes in environmental changes into the dynamics of an evolving happen very fast, environmental uncertainties and the very high level of competition often leads to a leader who decided to experience a failure. Indirect influence on various environmental changes that occur and cause a very big influence on successfully an organization. An organization will survive forward if it can adjust to the development of both the internal and external environment.

An organization can be able to utilize all available resources following the development of the environmental dynamics of an organization that needs appropriate strategies to overcome especially in the era disruptive this time. The higher the organization's ability to adapt to the changing dynamics of the environment of the organization more easily apply the right strategy and quickly won the competition is very tight. This can be done if an organization can perform the learning or the learning organization, explained that an organization that is built from the structure, culture, and strategies to develop and maximize the potential for learning in an organization (Bohnsack & Pinkse, 2017). A current or past era with the disruptive

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condition is the era of the products or services that create new markets, disrupt or destroy existing markets, and eventually replace the previous technology.

III. RESEARCH METHODS AND DISCUSSION

The method used is the descriptive qualitative analytic approach. Data collected through literature studies and fieldwork using interviews, observation and documentation study. Analysis of data through data reduction, data presentation, conclusion. The discussion of the identification of the problem, namely:

A. How Insight into Knowledge Management?

Knowledge management is the organization's activities in managing knowledge as an asset in which the various strategies the proper distribution of knowledge to the right people and in the period of rapid so that they are can be interact, share knowledge and apply it in their daily work to improve organizational performance. Experts in the field of information explaining that the information is the knowledge that is presented to a person in a form that can be understood or data that has been processed or arranged to present the facts that imply, while the knowledge derived from the relevant information is absorbed and integrated into one's mind, while knowledge relates to what is known and understood by a person and the information tends to be the case while the knowledge derived from information that is interpreted and integrated.

Knowledge is divided into two general categories: (1) tacit knowledge is knowledge in the form of experience, skill, understanding, as well as the rule of thumb, tacit knowledge stored in the mind (brain) individuals in an organization following their competence, (2) Explicit knowledge is a form of knowledge which has been documented, easily stored, copied, studied, more easily recorded, managed and utilized and transferred to another party. Both types (tacit and explicit) knowledge can be converted through a conversion process that is four socialization (sharing process), externalizing (the transfer of knowledge), combination (the transfer of knowledge through the system and applications) and internalization (The transfer of knowledge through a learning process). Knowledge management is built on four pillars, namely process, knowledge creation, knowledge transfer, the use of knowledge and knowledge storage.

B. How Is The Implementation Of Knowledge Management Related To The Effectiveness Of The Organization?

In the application of knowledge management in both the business sector and institutions out of the role of human resources. Institutions or organizations in carrying out their functions and roles can leverage to integrate the management organization with a comprehensive understanding and reflecting the impact of the advancement of information, thus the implementation of knowledge management is expected to improve the quality and competitiveness and effectiveness of the organization.

The role of information technology in the implementation of knowledge management should be viewed as a means to competitive advantage. Implementation of organizational management is seen as a strategic to something that involves people, to see the implementation of knowledge management concerning the effectiveness of the organization are as follows: (1) conduct a survey to determine how many people feel the benefits of the implementation of knowledge management, (2) find various examples of the problems that occurred in the organization and can quickly finish through the application knowledge management, (3) measuring the activity of the community of practice, for example, count the number of people who can interact with the application of knowledge management, (4) to discover how many activities business that produces something helpful of the implementation of knowledge management, (5) how many people can access information through the internet, (6) how many files of knowledge and practical experience in organizations that have used information technology, (7) how much existing knowledge assets that have updating

C. How the Implementation of Knowledge Management in Building Organizational Effectiveness in the Face of Environmental Dynamics in the Disruptive Era?

We are already facing a new era is the era of disruptive where the world has changed in various fields including the development of communication technology, the rise of the millennial generation, the need for mindset, challenge to face the competition very rapidly it is necessary strategies appropriate to deal with change and challenge which is dynamics environment that influences the effectiveness of an organization. In the era of globalization where changes in environmental changes occur very rapidly, the uncertainty of the environment and the level of competition is very high often cause a leader should be able to have a strategy in making organizational decisions, errors in reading the situation and overreact to changes in the dynamically changing environment will fail.

The organization will survive forward if managers can make the right decisions and quickly following the development of the internal and external environment. Several factors influence the effectiveness and success of an organization that is (1) factor

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strategies (market-oriented, product, customers satisfaction), (2) organizational factors that put more emphasis on effective leadership, policies, procedures, implementation of culture, employee behaviour, commitment, organizational strategy implementation), (3) employees (more emphasis on teamwork, communication between members of the organization, education, and motivation of employees), (4) the environment (more emphasis on the social, economic, technological, and competition). Management of the 21st century requires that we be able to deal with full disruptive agility and intelligence. Management used to be based on technology, human resource development methods, leadership, advanced production and business, the role of the State and global competitiveness. Disruptive is an innovation, which will be changed the entire old system with a new and potentially replaced the old with the new players, old technology which is too physical with the digital technology that produces something truly new and more useful. Disruptive will be creating a new world: digital, marketplace, virtual markets, and the need adaptive to change.

Disruptive has on economic development of both macro and micro, social, cultural and political. Several points regarding Disruption: (1) A process that does not happen instantly. Starting from the idea, research or experiment, and the manufacturing process, the development of the business model. When it works, entrants will expand its business to the point market bottom that overlooked the incumbent, then slowly grind up into segments that are already controlled by the incumbent (2) Entering the market with a business model is new, different to that already made the players a long time. Therefore, business model innovation to be important (3) Not all the disruption went on to become perpetrators of disruption or destroy the incumbent position (4) incumbent should not always turn into a disruptor. There are many strategies pursued incumbent bias, including the continuing sustainable innovation and forming another unit that serves disruptor (5) Technology is not a disruptor, but the enabler. In addition to IT, other new tools are needed to support the success (6) Disruption may cause deflation, prices drop, as disruptor start a low-cost strategy (7) The market has a response that can be divided by 2 is willing to accept and reject. Identified five triggers waves of disruption that occurred since 1980. Recorded in 2015, has passed about 20 episodes of surprise is divided into five categories of causes, namely: (1) Technology (especially IT), (2) Management theory (new methods of human resource management, leadership, production, and business), (3) Economic events (role of the state, the central bank, fluctuation supply-demand), (4) Global Competitiveness, and (5) Geopolitical (tensions between regions).

Facing the era disruptive with knowledge management as a base to do with the transformation and renewal in the elements contained in knowledge management, among others:

- a. Be adaptive a process to be able to adjust to the ever-changing needs flourish
- b. Continuous learning: a process that includes the combined result of the training, development and continuous learning
- c. Continuous improvement: improvement and continuous improvement (endlessly), paraded to better progress.

IV. CONCLUSION

Knowledge management is the organization's activities in managing knowledge as an asset in which the various strategies the proper distribution of knowledge to the right people and in the period of rapid so that they are can be interact, share knowledge and apply it in their daily work to improve organizational performance. In the era of globalization where changes in environmental changes occur very rapidly, the uncertainty of the environment and the level of competition is very high often cause a leader should be able to have a strategy in making organizational decisions, errors in reading the situation and overreact to changes in the dynamically changing environment will fail. The organization will survive forward if managers can make the right decisions and quickly following the development of the internal and external environment.

Several factors influence the effectiveness and success of an organization that is (1) factor strategies (market-oriented, product, customers satisfaction), (2) organizational factors that put more emphasis on effective leadership, policies, procedures, implementation of culture, employee behaviour, commitment, organizational strategy implementation), (3) employees (more emphasis on teamwork, communication between members of the organization, education, and motivation of employees), (4) the environment (more emphasis on the social, economic, technological, and competition).

Management of the 21st century requires that we be able to deal with full disruptive agility and intelligence. Management used to be based on technology, human resource development methods, leadership, advanced production and business, the role of the State and global competitiveness. Disruptive is an innovation, which will be changed the entire old system with a new and potentially replaced the old with the new players, old technology which is too physical with the digital technology that produces something new and more useful. Disruptive will be creating a new world: the digital marketplace, virtual markets, and the need adapting to change. Disruptive has on economic development of both macro and micro, social and political culture.

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Organizations should develop a strategy and system according to their needs. The big challenge occurs when developing a measuring tool, simplifying the process, handling of resistance to change, the weakness of the organization communicate, collect data, adapting the technology to process and benchmarking.

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